

DELIVERABLE

Project Number: 964591

Project Acronym: SMART-electron

Project Title: Ultrafast All-Optical Spatio-Temporal
Electron Modulators: Opening New Frontiers In Electron Microscopy

Funding Scheme: H2020-FETOPEN-2018-2020

Number of Work Package	WP6
Number of Deliverable	D6.7
Title of Deliverable	Graphic assets for Dissemination and Communication activities (third release)
Lead Beneficiary	QED
Due Date	M36

Start Date of Project: 01/05/2021

Duration: 48 months

Graphic assets for Dissemination and Communication activities (third release)

D6.7

Version 1.0

Authors:

Luca M.C. Giberti (QED)
R. Santucci (QED)

Reviewers:

Giovanni Maria Vanacore (UNIMIB)

Project funded by the European Commission within the FET OPEN Programme		
Dissemination Level		
P	Public	X
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Revision History

Revision	Authors	Organisation	Description
0.1	Raffaella Santucci	QED	First draft
0.2	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti R. Santucci	QED QED	First complete version
0.3	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti R. Santucci	QED QED	Second complete version - overall cleanup and insertion of text+images
0.4	R. Santucci	QED	Added jpgs of designs, intro and conclusions
0.5	Giovanni Maria Vanacore	UNIMIB	Review and comments, minor changes
0.6	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti R. Santucci	QED QED	Feedback integrated, overall revision, added links and further explanations/thoughts
0.7	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti R. Santucci Giovanni Maria Vanacore	QED QED UNIMIB	Overall revision
1.0	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti	QED	Revised final version incorporating reviewers' suggestions and minor amendments

Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Disclaimer

The sole responsibility for the content of this deliverable lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the REA nor the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1 INTRODUCTION - WHO WILL BE USING THESE DESIGNS AND THIS DELIVERABLE?	6
2 DESIGN PHILOSOPHY	7
2.1 NEW - Further Considerations For The Third Release	7
3 LIST OF THE GRAPHIC ASSETS THAT WERE PRODUCED	7
3.1 The Actual Design Process	10
3.2 Copywriting	14
3.3 Designs For The Second Release	15
3.4 NEW Further Designs For The Third Release	16
4 LOW-RESOLUTION COPIES OF THE DESIGNS (FIRST RELEASE)	17
5 LOW-RESOLUTION COPIES OF THE DESIGNS (SECOND RELEASE)	26
6 NEW LOW-RESOLUTION COPIES OF THE DESIGNS (THIRD RELEASE)	35
7 CONCLUSIONS	46
ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS	47
Short Name Of Participants	47
List Of Abbreviations	47

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a comprehensive overview of the production of all print and presentation materials used for the communication and dissemination of the SMART-electron project. This third and final release builds upon the foundations set by the first and second versions of these assets, which are extensively documented herein.

Details of the Update:

- **Chapter 1** offers a revised introduction that reflects the conclusion of our graphic asset development, marking the end of this phase.
- **Chapter 2** continues to explore the philosophical approach behind the design of our graphic materials, emphasising their crucial role in making a lasting first impression of the project.
- **Chapter 3** lists the designs that have been produced, providing a final account of how the design and copywriting processes have unfolded.
- **Chapter 4** and **Chapter 5** present low-resolution copies of the first and second releases of the designs, respectively.
- **Chapter 6** presents low-resolution copies of the third release of the designs.
- **Chapter 7**, now updated, encapsulates the conclusions and take-home messages derived from the work completed, highlighting this as the final set of updates for the graphic materials under this project phase.

As no further updates to these deliverables are foreseen in the workplan, all subsequent materials for dissemination activities will be comprehensively described in the final project report.

1 INTRODUCTION - WHO WILL BE USING THESE DESIGNS AND THIS DELIVERABLE?

Within SMART-electron the dissemination and communication materials are used by:

- All partners
- All WP leaders
- Particularly by the staff responsible for each institution's communication activities.

In addition, as this is a public document and is available on the project's website, it will be accessible by external parties interested in disseminating and communicating SMART-electron.

This deliverable has been updated periodically, according to the project's needs.

2 DESIGN PHILOSOPHY

The design of the printed materials was based on two simple but effective requirements: starting from the existing project logo, and tweaking the project website if necessary, we aimed to attain a graphic identity that is at the same time *distinctive* and *classic*. The branding guidelines as given in D6.3 were also drafted with this two-fold goal in mind. Achieving both a degree of timelessness and a striking design that 'speaks to everyone' has in turn two significant consequences.

A timeless and classic look means that the design is conceived to 'age well', which is one of QED's priorities given the fact that the project website, together with the graphic assets it contains, are required to stay up for at least 5 years after the end of project - which means no less than 9 years in the future.

On the other hand, a strong graphic statement that is simple, easy to identify, and based on universal proportions (such as for instance certain mathematical ratios) allows the use of the same design/theme for both dissemination and communication. This strong visual identity was consistently 'declined' in the various graphic & print designs, as detailed in chapter 3.

Both considerations translate into cost and labour savings for the project, especially with a view to its future upkeep/sustainability.

Another cost-saving consideration was the idea of designing templates for brochures and posters that the partners will be able to easily fill in and print locally as the need arises (see below).

2.1 NEW - FURTHER CONSIDERATIONS FOR THE THIRD RELEASE

The core philosophy guiding the development of our graphic assets remained consistent as we approached this third release. A primary focus was to address the evolving needs of SMART-electron's upcoming activities, including the final International Conference. In aiming to maintain a seamless continuity with previous designs, we also adapted to the practical demands of forthcoming events. These adaptations and enhancements, which include a range of new and updated promotional items designed to increase engagement and visibility, are detailed in Chapter 3.4.

3 LIST OF THE GRAPHIC ASSETS THAT WERE PRODUCED

In terms of graphic materials for dissemination and communication, the needs of such an ambitious project as SMART-electron are many. Broadly speaking, some printed assets are meant to be general-purpose, i.e. deployable anywhere without any changes, whilst others are event-specific, i.e. tailored to each specific SMART-electron International Conference or event. Based on the project schedule as well as on an evaluation of the overall progress so far (and in particular on D6.3 Dissemination and Communication Plan), the following assets were thus identified and then designed:

1. foldable two-sided general-purpose square Project brochure;
2. template for conference-specific A2 Project poster;
3. general-purpose 80x200 Project vinyl banner;
4. template for the A4 Project conference programme;
5. general-purpose SMART-electron-branded tote bag;

6. template for SMART-electron slides;
7. favicons and social media icons/banners;
8. graphic design guidelines;
9. novel colour scheme and layout for the conference-specific A2 Project poster;
10. designs for the conference-specific A4 book of abstracts, according to the new colour scheme;
11. novel colour scheme and interior design for the foldable two-sided general-purpose square Project brochure;
12. Web banner for the upcoming International Conference;
13. NEW SMART-electron-branded baseball cap;
14. NEW SMART-electron branded water bottle;
15. NEW SMART-electron USB drives;
16. NEW SMART-electron-branded stickers;
17. NEW SMART-electron interactive QR Code;
18. NEW SMART-electron-branded lanyard;
19. NEW SMART-electron-branded notebooks;
20. NEW SMART-electron-branded pen;
21. NEW SMART-electron-branded keychains;
22. NEW SMART-electron-branded mouse pads;
23. NEW SMART-electron-branded T-shirts;
24. NEW SMART-electron-branded mugs.

1) General-purpose two-fold square brochure, to be deployed at various events as a general presentation of the project. The choice of a square format is due to reasons of compatibility with the square aspect ratio favoured for online assets (Instagram, browser favicons, shortcut icons on mobiles, etc.).

2) Template for event-specific vertical A2 poster, printable as A3 if necessary. The choice of a standard ISO 216 / DIN format instead of more 'fashionable' ones translates into savings for the project and in no way diminishes the impact of the design. A2 was chosen as the largest possible format that can be hung without too much trouble in pinboards and public spaces – since, trivially, a larger format guarantees greater visibility. The design is compatible with printing in A3, which is significantly cheaper for small runs of digital prints.

3) General-purpose 80x200 standalone vinyl banner, to advertise and signal events taking place in a specific venue, such as conferences, seminars, lectures, press conferences, etc. The choice of PVC as the printing material makes the roll-up banner suitable for outdoor use as well.

4) Template for the event-specific A4 conference programmes, which provides readers with the schedule for all the topics of all the talks and all the posters presented at the conference, as well as a list of all participants. It is also meant as a memento of the conference for all participants.

5) General-purpose SMART-electron-branded tote bag, to be given to all conference participants as well as to guests.

6) Template for SMART-electron slide presentations. To be used by all partners when presenting on behalf of SMART-electron. A set of coherent graphic rules is given in the template.

7) Browser favicons and social media icons & banners were derived from the logo and optimised according to the various social media guidelines.

8) Graphic design guidelines for the correct deployment of graphic assets (including the Logo) were produced in the form of a PDF booklet, which was distributed to partners.

9) The new colour scheme and layout for the A2 poster is aimed at facilitating fast and convenient printing by Project partners, thus providing value for money. The poster can be printed as A3 if necessary.

10) The new design for the conference-specific A4 book of abstracts will allow the collection and easy browsing of all the contributions to the SMART-electron 2023 International Conference.

11) The new colour scheme was also used for the re-design of the general-purpose two-fold square brochure, which is now harmonised with the new Conference printed assets.

12) A new Web banner was designed and placed on the Project website homepage, in order to promote the 2023 International Conference.

13) NEW SMART-electron-branded baseball cap: This cap is intended as a casual yet fashionable piece of merchandise that increases the project's visibility. It serves as a wearable promotional item at outdoor events and casual gatherings, representing the project in everyday situations.

14) NEW SMART-electron branded water bottle: Designed for eco-friendly hydration, this durable water bottle features the SMART-electron branding and is ideal for conference attendees and team members alike. It promotes both sustainability and project visibility wherever it is used.

15) NEW SMART-electron USB drives: A practical giveaway item, these coloured USB drives are branded with the SMART-electron logo and pre-loaded with project information and resources. They are an essential tool for workshops, seminars, and meetings, providing participants with easy access to digital materials.

16) NEW SMART-electron-branded stickers: Fun and versatile, these stickers can be used on laptops, notebooks, and anywhere else to spread awareness of the project. They are designed to be eye-catching and can be distributed as a collectible item at various events.

17) NEW Interactive SMART-electron QR code: Integrated into the next print and digital materials, this QR code links directly to the project's website (or specific online resources if so desired), providing immediate access to further information about SMART-electron with just a simple scan.

18) NEW SMART-electron-branded lanyard: The lanyard is a functional and durable item for holding ID badges or keys, given to participants at all project-related events.

19) SMART-electron-branded notebooks: These custom notebooks are designed for practical use at conferences, workshops, or in daily tasks. The cover prominently displays the SMART-electron logo, emphasising the project's identity and unity.

20) SMART-electron-branded pen: The pen features the SMART-electron logo, complementing the notebooks to provide a cohesive branding experience. It is suitable for use at various events, subtly enhancing the project's visibility in professional settings - and serves as a practical keepsake that continues to promote the project long after the events.

21) SMART-electron-branded keychains: These keychains are both practical and stylish, featuring the SMART-electron logo.

22) SMART-electron-branded mouse pads: These mouse pads offer a smooth, durable surface for mouse operation and feature the SMART-electron branding prominently. They are ideal for use in office settings or at home, providing a constant visual connection to the project.

23) SMART-electron-branded T-shirts: Made from high-quality fabric, they ensure comfort and durability. The SMART ELECTRON logo is displayed prominently, making these shirts perfect for project events, casual outings, or as everyday wear to promote project visibility.

24) SMART-electron-branded mugs: These mugs are designed with the SMART ELECTRON logo, making them a great addition to any kitchen or office. They serve as a practical reminder of the project during coffee breaks or meetings.

Insofar as possible, SMART-electron designs are meant to be printed locally by partners, close to where they have to be deployed, in order to save on expenses and environmental impact. The designs are sent to partners with specific instructions as to the type of printing process, paper, and finish to be adopted, so as to ensure a consistently high standard of quality.

All the designs were optimised for offset printing but can be output as high-quality laser or inkjet prints if necessary.

3.1 THE ACTUAL DESIGN PROCESS

Work on the designs for SMART-electron's printed materials was conceived from the outset to evolve based on the graphic design done previously for the project: from the outset, we sought to expand as a coherent whole the system of typesetting and design rules underlying the project's graphic identity. Hence, starting from the existing logo and website (described in D6.1 Project Logo and Webpage), two different concepts were developed and explored.

The first one consists of evoking photons and electrons through the stylisation and extensive repetition of the S and the E in the project logo. The curved elements of the S and the straight elements of the E can in fact be thought of as corresponding to the photon and electron lines in Feynman diagrams. This dichotomy is appropriate for SE, which is all about shaping electron matter waves by using photons. At the same time, the curved and the straight element can be viewed as symbolic of the wave/particle duality which is one of the defining features of Quantum Mechanics.

The second concept revolves around the idea of the correspondence between theory and experiment. The inspiration for this was a figure in the 2018 Nature Communications paper on attosecond control of free electrons by Vanacore et al¹.

¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-018-05021-x.pdf>

The starting point for the 'theory vs. experiment' concept for the graphic assets:
 the plots in <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-018-05021-x.pdf>

In the figure, the theoretical prediction for the light field amplitude vs. electron energy loss plot for the light-electron interaction is compared with the plot obtained through measurement. Since the interplay between theory/simulation and experiment is at the very heart of physics, we thought of applying an analogous graphic stylisation to the SMART-electron logotype, whereby the smooth predictions of theory are symbolised by the anti-aliased, vector-graphics version of the SMART-electron logotype, whereas the pixelated and noisy outcome of experiment is represented by the same logotype with added spatial distortion and rasterised with large pixels.

Early sketches for the poster (L) and the vinyl banner (R) based on the 'theory vs. experiment' concept

The same dichotomy was exploited for the inner fold of the brochure, where the two plots from the above paper mirror one another, with the symmetry about the vertical axis broken by the theory-vs-experiment discrepancy.

As to the use of colour, we followed our custom of relying on strong contrasts and simple colour schemes. In particular, we sought to build on the palette we chose for the website - by adopting the lime yellow we used for the webpages and logo, as well as its complementary colour for selected elements, such as the inner fold of the brochure:

Two early versions of the inner fold of the brochure based on the 'theory vs. experiment' concept and using the colour complement to the lime green of the Logo

In terms of paper formats, for speed of print and best value for money, we adopted standard DIN formats whenever possible - for example for the A2 poster for events. The brochure and the vinyl banner are an exception to our self-imposed "DIN-only" rule: we opted for a square brochure with a single inner fold due to reasons of compatibility with the square aspect ratio used in Instagram, as well as for browser favicons and link icons on mobile platforms. Having a unified design for all these assets -Instagram posts, favicons, mobile icons- makes a lot of sense since the SMART-electron presence across platforms is more immediately recognisable this way. The vinyl banner has a custom aspect ratio due to the brand-specific aspect ratio of the available blanks on which it is printed.

In the end, the first 'wave vs. particle' concept was deemed more impactful and won over the second one, which only survives in the inner fold of the brochure. Having settled on the main concept and proportions, special care was taken in considering the interplay of the designs with the type of paper and of printing method intended for each of the assets/formats. Then we proceeded to consistently 'decline' the leitmotiv in the various designs, which are shown in the next chapter. Throughout the design phase, all the guidelines regarding the use of the various official logos were observed.

3.2 COPYWRITING

Similar considerations of simplicity and efficacy were adopted for the copywriting. The latter, insofar as possible, eschewed lingo in favour of clear and simple explanations, understandable by the general public, but also providing meaningful information for specialists. The text can be read from the second figure in the next chapter.

3.3 DESIGNS FOR THE SECOND RELEASE

New designs for some of the conference-specific A2 poster, the A4 book of abstracts cover, and the square brochures were conceived for the 2023 SMART-electron International Conference. The general requirement was that -whilst in line with existing graphic assets and rules- the new designs should be able to stand out in 'crowded' places, such as billboards and pinboards. We found that introducing an element of colour in the main *leitmotiv* of the posters and covers satisfied this need, whilst allowing a neat form of colour coding for the three remaining Project events:

The new designs for the A4 book of abstracts for the SMART-electron 2023 International Conference and for further editions of the same event

The underlying SMART-electron colour scheme for print was also reversed, switching from white over black to black over white. This choice makes printing easier and cheaper for the hosting partner, enabling them to print the new designs directly with laser on inkjet printers, if necessary. This facilitates things, since large black surfaces are best printed via proper offset printing, or, better still, printed on black paper via hot stamping or screen printing; all these options are more expensive than direct printing on one partner's own printer.

Another decision we took in order to ease printing requirements was to employ a colour that is vivid but still within the standard CMYK and RGB gamuts used for printing. The Project thus retains its standard fluorescent palette for the website and for other online or non physical assets, whilst employing black, white, and primary yellow for printed, conference-specific graphic assets.

The foldable two-sided general-purpose square Project brochure was updated according to the new colour scheme. The Project logo in the brochure was left in its black version, so as to signify the general-purpose nature of the brochure. This has the added advantage of enabling a single print run for the brochures for all future conferences.

A Web banner advertising the 2023 International Conference was added to the Project website. The choice of photo and of layout was done so as to attract prospective physical participants, who might be interested in the beauty and cultural sights of the Conference location.

All the above choices contribute to providing value for money.

Low-resolution copies and images of the new designs are provided in chapter 5 of this same document.

3.4 NEW FURTHER DESIGNS FOR THE THIRD RELEASE

For this release, we have expanded our range of dissemination materials with several new designs for branded objects and updated existing items to enhance the visibility and practical utility of the SMART-electron project at various events and conferences. These additions were conceived to align with our established graphic standards while offering distinctive, functional, and engaging new ways to promote project awareness.

Among these, the introduction of items such as the SMART-electron branded water bottles and USB drives caters to the modern needs of conference attendees, providing them with useful tools that carry the project's branding. Similarly, practical items such as the SMART-electron branded baseball caps and lanyards enhance the informal engagement opportunities, making the project presence felt in a variety of settings, from casual gatherings to formal presentations. Like most of the output of dissemination and communication, these branded objects are meant to ensure that instances of the project's presence will outlast its official four-year duration.

The design choices for these materials were dictated by the necessity to stand out and yet remain cohesive with our existing visual identity. For instance, the integration of an interactive QR code directly connects physical materials with digital resources, ensuring seamless access to comprehensive project information. These materials are designed to be versatile and engaging, significantly enhancing the project's visibility and interaction with diverse audiences.

Low-resolution copies and images of the new designs are provided in Chapter 6 of this document, offering a preview of the materials that stakeholders and participants will encounter in future project interactions.

4 LOW-RESOLUTION COPIES OF THE DESIGNS (FIRST RELEASE)

The SMART-electron two-fold brochure

The SMART-electron vertical A2 poster, which is also the template for event-specific posters

The SMART-electron vinyl banner

The SMART-electron vinyl banner

*The SMART-electron template for conference programmes
(outer cover)*

The SMART-electron tote bags

Templates for SMART-electron slides

SMART-electron browser favicon (L) and Facebook/Whatsapp group icon (R)

SMART-electron Springboard icon next to those of the [Q-SORT](#) and [MINEON](#) EC projects

SMART-electron Facebook banners

Select pages from the SMART-electron graphic design guidelines booklet

5 LOW-RESOLUTION COPIES OF THE DESIGNS (SECOND RELEASE)

The new design for the SMART-electron International Conference poster

The new design for the 2023 SMART-electron International Conference poster

The new SMART-electron book of abstracts cover

New SMART-electron book of abstracts internal pages

The new SMART-electron two-fold brochure

The new SMART-electron 2023 International Conference banner

6 NEW LOW-RESOLUTION COPIES OF THE DESIGNS (THIRD RELEASE)

NEW SMART-electron-branded baseball cap

NEW SMART-electron branded water bottle

NEW SMART-electron-branded USB drives

NEW SMART-electron-branded stickers

NEW interactive SMART-electron QR code

NEW SMART-electron-branded lanyard

NEW SMART-electron-branded notebooks

NEW SMART-electron-branded pens

NEW SMART-electron-branded keychains

NEW SMART-electron-branded mouse pads

NEW SMART-electron-branded T-shirts

NEW SMART-electron-branded mugs

7 CONCLUSIONS

This document marks the completion of the third release of the SMART-electron project's dissemination materials, showcasing a strategic expansion and refinement in line with our ongoing objectives. The involvement as a partner of a professional media production company (QED) is beneficial for the quality of the designs and of the copywriting, which dynamically reflect the evolving needs of the project.

In this latest release, QED introduced several new promotional items, including SMART-electron-branded baseball caps, water bottles, USB drives, lanyards, and interactive QR codes. These new items complement our existing suite of materials and are designed to enhance both visibility and engagement at various project-related events, particularly the upcoming SMART-electron final International Conference.

The process reaffirmed the importance of scheduling adequate 'buffer time' for revisions and approvals, accommodating changes requested by partners or institutions whose logos are featured. This approach helps manage the refinement iterations, which tend to increase with the number of stakeholders involved.

Pre-production quality checks remain essential, ensuring the accurate representation of text, logos, colours, and graphics before final printing. This diligence is critical not only for maintaining brand integrity but also for the practical utility of the materials, such as the correct folding of updated brochures.

The addition of new digital and physical assets, including updated general-purpose, two-sided square project brochures and branded stickers, has significantly broadened our toolkit for effective communication. These new elements are designed to ensure that the SMART-electron project maintains a cohesive and engaging presence across both physical and digital realms.

Partners are now equipped with a comprehensive array of updated and new materials, enabling them to effectively plan and execute their own dissemination activities. This suite of resources ensures that the SMART-electron project is well-presented and continues to make a significant impact in all its engagements.

ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
1 UNIVERSITA' DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO-BICOCCA	ITALY	UNIMIB
2 ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE EPFL	SWITZERLAND	EPFL
3 FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE CIENCIES FOTONIQUES	SPAIN	ICFO
4 TECHNION - ISRAEL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY	ISRAEL	TECHNION
5 CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	ITALY	CNR
6 HOLOEYE PHOTONICS AG	GERMANY	HOLOEYE
7 QED FILM & STAGE PRODUCTIONS LTD	UK	QED

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL